

Convergent Nicomachus Averaging

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A previous article **[1]** explored an iterative scheme inspired by the Nicomachus identity

$$\sum_{n=1}^N n = \left(\sum_{n=1}^N n^3\right)^{1/2}$$

for the integer string $\{n\} = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$.

More generally, for any string $\{s\}$ of length N the OCTAVE code

```
N=length(s); % N>1  
k=1:N;  
C=sqrt(cumsum(s).^3)./k;
```

yields a string of convergents $\{C\}$ for any fixed N off the appropriate averaging scheme.

The integer string $\mathbf{s=1:N}$ for $N = 10,000$ generated matched convergence output - within precision bounds - derived somewhat differently in **[1]**:

```
for k=1:N,C(k)=sqrt(k*((k+1)/2)^3);,end
```

Now, the image below charts the difference

C - floor(C)

a difference whose kurtosis is 1.800617317069152, that of uniform noise; perhaps a useful way to generate digitally such random sequences.

Next, for primes up to 10,000 (9,552 to be exact), OCTAVE code yields

```
p=primes(10000);,N=length(p);
```

The convergents counter **Cp** - estimated using the boxed commands - is shown below.

Top tier: C_p , bottom tier: $C_p - \text{floor}(C_p)$, whose kurtosis 1.802739689516831 again is near uniform noise.

Of the 9,552 primes, $\text{floor}(C_p)$ had 527 primes.

Now, the **Fibonacci** sequence $\mathbf{F}(n)$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ is the sequence

$$\mathbf{F} = [1; 1; 2; 3; 5; 8; 13; 21; 34; 55; \dots]$$

with convergence counter \mathbf{CF} estimated as previously. The cumulative sum of \mathbf{F} is actually greater than \mathbf{CF} early on, though only until the 8th term; see the plotted difference ($\mathbf{CF} - \text{cumsum}(\mathbf{F})$) below.

Next, the **Lucas** sequence $\mathbf{L}(n)$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ is the sequence

$$\mathbf{L} = [1; 3; 4; 7; 11; 18; 29; 47; 76; 123; \dots]$$

with corresponding convergence counter \mathbf{CL} ; except for the 1st term, the cumulative sum of \mathbf{L} is greater than its convergence counter (only) until the 7th term; see their difference below.

While it is well-known [3], that the ratio

$$L(n)/F(n) \rightarrow 5^{1/2}$$

for sufficiently large n , the ratio of the Lucas/Fibonacci convergence counters

$$CL/CF$$

reaches a (numerically) constant value of **3.343701524882110**;; see the graph below.

This limiting value (curiously) happens to equal $5^{3/4}$.

A **Tribonacci** sequence **TF(n)**, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, is defined as

$TF(1) = 1, TF(2) = 1, TF(3) = 2, TF(n+3) = TF(n+2) + TF(n+1) + TF(n)$. Thus

$$TF = [1;1;2;4;7;13;24;44;81;149;...]$$

with convergence counter **CTF**.

Similarly, a **Trilucas** sequence **TL(n)**, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, is defined as

$TL(1) = 1, TL(2) = 3, TL(3) = 4, TL(n+3) = TL(n+2) + TL(n+1) + TL(n)$. Thus

$$TL = [1;3;4;8;15;27;50;92;169;311;...]$$

with convergence counter **CTL**.

Numerically, the ratio

$$TL/TF \rightarrow 2.087378025384154 \approx 3^{2/3}$$

while

$$CTL/CTF \rightarrow 3.015793916152793$$

These ratios are graphed below for $N = 1:100$.

References

- [1] Wikipedia article on Nicomachus.
- [2] A. Cusmariu, 'A proof of the Arithmetic Mean-Geometric Mean Inequality'; <https://zenodo.org/records/3953032> (Jul 2020)
- [3] T. Koshy's, 'Fibonacci and Lucas Numbers with Applications', Vol.1; Wiley, 2018.